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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Air pollution exposure contributes to millions of deaths and a substantial loss of healthy life years annually. Long-term exposure to PM_{2.5} is a major risk factor for premature mortality. Iğdır was recorded as the most polluted city in Europe in terms of PM_{2.5} pollution in 2021 and 2022. In this study, we aimed to examine the PM_{2.5} concentrations in Iğdır for the year 2023 and assess air pollution-attributable mortality using the AirQ+ software.

Materials and Methods: This ecological study used 2023 PM_{2.5} data from Iğdır air quality monitoring station, provided by the National Air Quality Monitoring Network. The impact of long-term PM_{2.5} exposure on mortality in individuals was assessed using the AirQ+ software. Mortality and population data were sourced from the Turkish Statistical Institute. The cut-off value for the annual average PM_{2.5} concentration is set at 10 µg/m³, in accordance with the WHO guideline. Based on these data, the estimated attributable proportion, estimated number of attributable cases, and estimated number of attributable cases per 100,000 population at risk were calculated.

Results: In 2023, the annual average PM_{2.5} concentration in Iğdır was 47.55 ± 68.03 µg/m³, with the highest concentrations recorded in January (174.29 µg/m³) and December (113.58 µg/m³). The lowest levels occurred in June and July (12.46 µg/m³ and 12.85 µg/m³, respectively). According to AirQ+ software, 173 deaths among individuals aged 30 and above were attributable to air pollution, resulting in a mortality rate of 181.49 per 100,000 population.

Conclusion: In 2023, PM_{2.5} concentrations in Iğdır province remained notably high, resulting in a significant mortality rate linked to air pollution. To reduce the health impacts of air pollution, coordinated policies involving local governments, national authorities, and academic institutions are essential, along with promoting renewable energy sources and incentivizing the reduction of fossil fuel use. Furthermore, increasing air quality monitoring stations and conducting follow-up studies will provide valuable insights for managing health risks.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Air pollution, air quality, mortality rate, Iğdır, Türkiye

INTRODUCTION

Exposure to air pollution is associated with millions of deaths and a significant number of lost healthy life years each year. The health burden linked to air pollution is now considered comparable to other major global risk factors, including poor dietary habits and tobacco smoking. Moreover, air pollution is increasingly acknowledged as the leading environmental threat to human health (World Health Organization, 2021). Epidemiological studies have demonstrated that long-term exposure to fine particulate matter with an

aerodynamic diameter of 2.5 micrometers or less (PM2.5) is a significant risk factor for premature mortality and adverse health effects (Pala et al., 2021). Outdoor air pollution poses a significant public health challenge for Türkiye. Iğdır, located in the eastern part of Türkiye, was recorded as the most polluted city in Europe in terms of PM2.5 pollution in 2021 and 2022 (Öztürk et al., 2023).

The AirQ+ software developed by the World Health Organization European Regional Office is designed to calculate the health effects of air pollution on a specific population. Based on evidence from epidemiological cohort studies that examine the relationship between environmental air pollution concentration levels and mortality risks in exposed populations, users can estimate the adverse health impacts attributable to exposure to a specific level of air pollution within a defined time period for the population of interest (World Health Organization, 2021).

In this study, we aimed to examine the PM2.5 concentrations in Iğdır for the year 2023 and assess air pollution-attributable mortality using the AirQ+ software.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This ecological study was conducted using data from the air quality monitoring station located in Iğdır city center. The data on PM2.5 concentrations were obtained from the National Air Quality Monitoring Network of the Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Environment, Urbanization, and Climate Change for the period between January 1, 2023, and December 31, 2023 (National Air Quality Monitoring Network, 2025). Based on these data, the annual and monthly average PM2.5 concentrations ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) were calculated. Long-term exposure to PM2.5 and its association with mortality in the population aged 30 years and older was assessed using AirQ+ 2.2, a software tool developed by the World Health Organization for health risk assessment of air pollution (World Health Organization, 2025). For the year 2023, data on the total population of Iğdır province, the population aged 30 years and older, the number of deaths among individuals aged 30 years and older, and mortality data categorized by causes of death were obtained from the Turkish Statistical Institute (TÜİK, 2025). Deaths due to external injury causes and poisonings were excluded from the analysis. The cut-off value for the annual average PM2.5 concentration is set at $10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, in accordance with the WHO guideline. Based on these data, the estimated attributable proportion, estimated number of attributable cases, and estimated number of attributable cases per 100,000 population at risk were calculated using the AirQ+ software. As this ecological study was based on publicly available data, ethical approval was not required.

RESULTS

According to the data from the air quality monitoring station in the center of Iğdır Province in 2023, the annual average PM2.5 concentration was $47.55 \pm 68.03 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The highest monthly average PM2.5 concentrations were recorded in January and December ($174.29 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $113.58 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively). The lowest monthly average PM2.5 concentrations occurred in July and June ($12.46 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $12.85 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively). An increase was observed in the first three and last three months of the year, with average concentrations exceeding $25 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ during these six months. The monthly average PM2.5 concentrations for the Iğdır air quality monitoring station in 2023 is presented in Figure 1.

According to the analysis conducted using the AirQ+ software, the estimated number of deaths attributable to air pollution among individuals aged 30 and above in Iğdır in 2023 was 173, accounting for 25.1% of total deaths in this age group. The air pollution-attributable mortality rate in Iğdır was found to be 181.49 per 100,000 population. The estimated attributable proportion, number of deaths, and mortality rate due to air pollution in Iğdır in 2023 are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Estimated Attributable Proportion, Number of Deaths, and Mortality Rate Due to Air Pollution in Iğdır Province, 2023

Estimated Attributable Proportion (%)			Estimated Number of Attributable Deaths			Estimated Number of Attributable Deaths (per 100,000 Population at Risk)		
Central	Lower	Upper	Central	Lower	Upper	Central	Lower	Upper
25.1	19.65	27.65	173	136	191	181.49	142.11	199.91

DISCUSSION

PM_{2.5} is a hazardous outdoor air pollutant associated with a wide range of health problems, primarily affecting the cardiovascular and respiratory systems (Feng et al., 2016). Pope et al. emphasize that a 10 µg/m³ increase in particulate matter concentration is associated with a 4% increase in all-cause mortality and a 6% increase in deaths from cardiopulmonary diseases (Pope et al., 2002). Another study found that a 10 µg/m³ increase in PM_{2.5} levels led to a 15–27% rise in cancer-related mortality (Turner et al., 2011). In 2023, the average PM_{2.5} concentration in Iğdır was found to be significantly above the World Health Organization's recommended annual limit of 10 µg/m³. Despite being a low-population province in Türkiye with limited industrial activity and vehicle traffic, PM_{2.5} pollution in Iğdır is particularly severe during the winter months. This phenomenon is largely attributed to meteorological conditions and the widespread use of low-quality fuels. Although air quality improves somewhat in the summer, poor air quality is still observed, which may be due to local wind erosion (Öztürk et al., 2023).

In our study, the estimated attributable proportion related to long-term PM_{2.5} exposure was 25%, with a mortality rate of 181 per 100,000 population in Iğdır. A previous study with a similar methodology, which assessed all cities in Türkiye for the year 2018, reported a higher attributable proportion of 28.17% for Iğdır, ranking it first among all provinces. The mortality rate in that study was 214 per 100,000 population (Pala et al., 2021). Although a slight decline was observed, the persistently high air pollution-related mortality in Iğdır in both studies underscores the urgent need for effective air quality management strategies and targeted public health interventions to mitigate the adverse health effects of air pollution.

In a study conducted in Konya, similar calculations for the years 2017, 2018, and 2019 estimated the attributable proportion as 20.77%, 15.44%, and 12.02%, respectively (Filiz, 2023).

Additionally, Pala et al. identified 28 provinces in Türkiye where this proportion was below 10% (Pala et al., 2021). These regional variations underscore the heterogeneous nature of air pollution exposure and its associated health impacts across different regions of the country. Differences in attributable proportions may be influenced by various factors, including local air quality conditions, demographic characteristics, healthcare access, and environmental policies. However, the findings of our study indicate a substantial public health burden attributable to long-term PM_{2.5} exposure in Iğdır.

CONCLUSION

In our study, it was found that PM_{2.5} concentrations in Iğdır province remained significantly high in 2023, leading to a considerable mortality rate associated with air pollution. To mitigate the adverse health effects of air pollution, coordinated policies should be developed among local governments, national authorities, and academic institutions. The adoption of alternative and renewable energy sources should be encouraged, and incentives should be provided for the gradual reduction of fossil fuel use. In regions like Iğdır, which are topographically sensitive to air pollution, urban planning should be conducted with careful consideration of

environmental factors. Additionally, the number of air quality monitoring stations should be increased, and the regional distribution of these stations should be expanded to provide more comprehensive coverage. Well-designed follow-up studies are also needed to monitor the long-term health effects of air pollution and its impact on public health.

With the joint contributions of primary care providers, especially family physicians and public health specialists, significant progress can be made in early diagnosis of air pollution-related health problems and in raising environmental health awareness. Integrating an environmental health perspective into routine family medicine practices will be invaluable in strengthening community resilience to air pollution.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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